

ROMANIC LOANS AND THEIR ADAPTATION AND ASSIMILATION IN THE VOCABULARY SYSTEM OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Introduction

The relevance of the study of loanwords in the English language is associated, firstly, with the importance of studying the development of the English language, which, in the process of its long history of development, has adopted a significant number of foreign words from different languages and which have retained their original form.

Aim and tasks of the research: in this paper, the researcher reviews and studies a number of words of Romanic origin in the English word stock due to the Etymological Dictionary and, with the help of the examples enlisted, in that way confirms the topic`s significance in the modern linguistics.

The object of the research is Romanic language loanwords and their role of the English language.

The subject of the scientific paper is Romanic loans and their adaptation and assimilation in the vocabulary system of the English language.

Research methods: The following research methods are used in research work:

1. General scientific methods: analysis, synthesis, generalization, comparison
2. The method of analysis of scientific and scientific-methodical publications, highlighting the conceptual provisions of scientific knowledge
3. Linguistic methods proper: continuous sampling method, content analysis, etymological analysis of words.

The scientific novelty of the work lies, firstly, in the fact that in the process of studying the problems of borrowed vocabulary, we formulated our definition of the concept of “loanwords” and, secondly, the selection and etymological analysis of non-assimilated words taken from foreign languages recorded in English dictionaries.

Practical value and degree of the work lies in the fact that the systematization in the classification of assimilated borrowings will help in the future to a clearer and structured description of such vocabulary for scientific and educational purposes. Observations on the identified tendencies in the use of loanwords can be used in further descriptions of the process of borrowing, borrowed words, as well as in the preparation of lexicographic works and teaching aids of various types, which will be good helpers for the further investigations of future linguists.

The results obtained: lies in the fact that the results of the research work make a certain contribution in the development of Lexicology, Stylistics and that’s why it might help in the further research of this field; different definitions and classifications suggested by different scholars were gathered in this work. The results obtained can be used in further studies of the problems of Romanic Languages.

General summary and recommendations lies in the fact that the systematization in the classification of assimilated borrowings will help in the future to a clearer and structured description of such vocabulary for scientific and educational purposes. Observations on the identified tendencies in the use of loanwords can be used in further descriptions of the process of borrowing, borrowed words, as well as in the preparation of lexicographic works and teaching aids of various types, which will be good helpers for the further investigations of future linguists.

Conclusion

This thesis has revealed that the Present-Day English language continues to expand its vocabulary by means of loanwords from other languages. Even if

borrowing is no longer the major source of new words as it was mainly during the Middle English and the Early Modern English period, still there is a number of words coming into its lexicon. Such borrowing arises nowadays mainly from the spread of mass media, trade, or immigration.

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